

Geospatial and Structural Equation Modeling of Deforestation Risk in Uganda using Google Earth Engine

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Summary

Conventional deforestation risks models rely on linear approaches, failing to account for causal relationships among drivers. Yet several factors such as energy demand, urbanisation and agricultural expansion play different roles in deforestation. We propose a novel method integrating GIS-based spatial analysis and structural equation modeling to quantify direct and indirect effects of deforestation drivers. Results show that energy demand is a primary driver of deforestation and urbanization, while urbanization itself does not directly cause deforestation but influences indirectly through increased energy demand. This scalable model offers insights to support decision-making for balancing climate, urbanisation, energy security, and forest conservation.

KEYWORDS: Geospatial Modelling, Structural Equation Modeling, Energy Demand, Deforestation, SDG 7, SDG 13

1. Introduction

Deforestation, the permanent removal or clearing of forests for non-forest uses is a major environmental, energy, and climate security challenge, contributing 12–20% of global atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (Watson & Schalatek, 2020). Despite international commitments, such as the COP26 pledge to halt and reverse deforestation by 2030 (Fairchild, 2022) and the EU's 2023 law aiming at deforestation-free supply chains (Cesar de Oliveira et al., 2024), global forest loss continues. Between 2001 and 2023, over 480 million hectares of forests were lost worldwide, releasing more than 200 gigatons of CO₂ emissions (GFW, 2024). Within this period, Africa was most affected, with an annual net forest loss of 3.94 million hectares (FAO, 2020). Within Africa, Uganda faces consistent decline in forest cover, with an annual deforestation rate of 1.44% (FAOSTAT, 2020; MWE, 2022). The reliance on traditional biomass, primarily firewood and charcoal, has been identified as a major driver of deforestation, as it supports over 94% of household energy needs (MWE, 2022; UBOS, 2022). However, deforestation extends beyond direct energy demand, with underlying socio-economic, infrastructural, and accessibility-related factors exerting complex and interactive pressures across the country's landscapes (Mutesi et al., 2021).

Uganda's rapid urban population growth, increasing from 3,764,273 in 2001 to 13,005,977 in 2023, has significantly contributed to urbanization-driven deforestation. Over this period, the country has lost 1.10 million hectares (Mha) of tree cover, representing a 14% decline, and has released 500 million metric tons of CO₂ emissions (GFW, 2024). Despite these negative trends, the specific contributions of urban expansion, infrastructure development, and associated socio-economic factors to deforestation remain inadequately understood. According to Prochazka et al., (2023), urban expansion can lead to localized deforestation. However, predominant forces behind deforestation are many including agricultural expansion, energy demands, and urbanization. This underscores the complexity of

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pinpointing deforestation drivers, requiring empirical data to develop targeted, sustainable interventions.

Existing research in Uganda investigating deforestation drivers such as the GIS-based studies of Call et al., (2017) and field-survey analyses of Twongyirwe et al., (2018) do not account for underlying relationships amongst multiple drivers. These approaches rely on longitudinal datasets and linear models to establish direct correlations between deforestation and its drivers, which fail to capture the complex causative relationships that exist between deforestation and underlying urbanisation and other drivers. Additionally, current deforestation risk assessment models (Bamwesigye & Yeboah, 2022; Forest Policy Trade and Finance, 2024) focus on singular variables, such as land use or agricultural expansion, without incorporating the interdependent and dynamic interplay between multiple drivers. As a result, these models oversimplify the drivers of deforestation, limiting their effectiveness in informing evidence-based policy interventions.

Recent advancements in geospatial technologies, particularly open-access Landsat and Sentinel satellite remote sensing along with statistical modelling, present new opportunities to analyse the complex relationships between deforestation drivers (Turner et al., 2015). The computational demands of satellite data processing make it expensive. However, Google Earth Engine (GEE), an open-access cloud-based platform, facilitates large-scale satellite data processing and analysis (Gorelick et al., 2017). Additionally, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) serves as a robust statistical tool for examining causal relationships between deforestation and its underlying factors (Santibáñez-Andrade et al., 2015). This study employed geospatial and statistical modelling within GEE to analyse deforestation risk and its relationship with energy demand, and other factors. The research utilised GIS-based spatial analysis to prepare datasets, and integrated SEM to quantify the direct and indirect effects of several deforestation risk factors. SEM provided the statistical framework for modelling latent constructs such as energy demand and accessibility, while geospatial analysis allowed for high-resolution mapping of deforestation hotspots and risk factors. Raster-based datasets, including land use land cover changes, nighttime lights, population density, road-access networks, urban travel times and electric grid infrastructure were used to provide a comprehensive assessment of deforestation drivers in Uganda.

2. Proposed Method

The methodological flow diagram our novel approach is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 Proposed geospatial and statistical model flow diagram.

2.1 Datasets and variables.

We developed a Python based implementation in GEE (Abudu et al., 2025) to prepare deforestation risks variables from datasets (**Table 1**) and export to Microsoft Comma Separated Variable (CSV) format per sub-region. All raster datasets were pre-processed at 30 metre spatial resolution and projected to Uganda’s local projection of EPSG:32636. The considered change period is 2015 – 2020, due to the availability of energy demand proxy dataset. In the SEM step, several hypotheses, and pathways (**Table 2**) were formulated from literature, then a measurement model was graphically developed (**Figure 2**), and an optimal structural model in Python’s Semopy package (Igolkina & Meshcheryakov, 2020).

Table 1 Datasets used in the study

Data	Scale and year	Purpose	Source
Landcover	30 m raster 2005, 2015 and 2020.	30m raster data for 2005, 2015 and 2020. Used to extract deforestation	Produced from Landsat and Sentinel
VIIRS Nighttime Lights	500 m raster for 2015, 2020	Proxy to indicated economic activities and energy demand	Ingested in GEE
Urban travel time	500 m raster data for 2017	Lower urban areas indicate high	FAO
CHIRPS daily Rainfall	5566 m raster for 2015 and 2020	Data for climate	Ingested in GEE
ERA5 daily Temperature	27830 m raster for 2015 and 2020	Data for climate	Ingested in GEE
Population	30 m population per pixel data for 2015 and 2020.	Proxy for increased energy demand and urbanisation	Uganda Bureau of Statistics
Road network	Vector data	Proxy for urbanisation and infrastructure	
Electricity grid	Vector data	Proxy for infrastructural development	

Table 2 Developed hypotheses for structural equation graphical development.

Category	Hypothesis	Accept or Reject
Direct effects	H1: Energy demand is positively influenced by urbanisation.	Accepted
	H2: Energy demand is positively influenced by infrastructure.	Partially supported
	H3: Deforestation risk is positively influenced by energy demand.	Accepted
Indirect effects	H4: Urbanisation increased energy demand influencing deforestation risk	Partially supported
Moderation effects	H5: The effect of urbanisation on energy demand is moderated by climate.	Rejected

2.2 Model calibration and estimation.

The structural model was calibrated using a Maximum Likelihood Weighted (MLW) method. We estimated the model to determine optimal model using the Sequential Least Squares Quadratic Programming (SLSQP). SLSQP is a constrained nonlinear optimization algorithm that minimizes a function subject to both equality and inequality constraints, evading limitations of linear models in analysing causative relationships. By using both MLW and SLSQP in SEM, we achieved robust estimation (using MLW) and enforced specific variable constraints within the deforestation drivers (using SLSQP). We assessed the model fitness using several parameters such as Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.994, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) = 0.994, and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) = 0.079.

Figure 2 Estimated graphical paths of the structured equation model.

3. Results and Discussion

From **Figure 2**, the key drivers of energy demand are urbanisation (+1.44), and Infrastructure (+0.01). Within infrastructure, electric grid (+8.08) presents the highest influence, according to code implementation in Abudu et al., (2025). Higher energy demand increases the risk of deforestation (+0.01), which according to Uganda’s literature is due to increased charcoal and firewood consumption (MWE, 2022; UBOS, 2022). Equally infrastructural development (e.g., roads, buildings, power lines) leads to deforestation (+0.01). Conversely, changes in climate (rainfall and temperature change) and urbanisation are shown to reduce deforestation risks in Uganda. Generally in Uganda, deforestation is major in rural areas for socio-economic reasons (Mutesi et al., 2021). The recent increased reforestation drives since 2015, is leading to socio-economic shifts reducing rural deforestation pressures but shifting energy demand-driven deforestation elsewhere as rural-urban migration increases.

Results from **Figure 3**, showing large scale deforestation away from the southern built-up areas of Kampala, the capital of Uganda. Charcoal productions are conducted in rural forest neighbourhoods of

northern Uganda and transported to urban and per-urban communities in the southern region. This is supported by the distribution of nighttime lights shown in **Figure 4**. In Uganda nighttime lights are mostly common in urban areas and therefore has significant positive influence on both energy demand and negative influence on urbanisation. For the rejected hypothesis (H5), we note that including additional evidence showing how climate variables (e.g., temperature, rainfall) influence the urbanization-energy demand relationship could influence this hypothesis.

Figure 3 Land use land cover map for Uganda, 2005 and 2020

Figure 4 Normalised nighttime lights as a proxy for energy demand in 2015 (A) and 2020 (B).

Figure 5 Correlation between the different variables used in the estimation of optimal model.

4. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates an innovative approach that leverages open-access satellite imagery and the power of Google Earth Engine (GEE) to model energy demand and deforestation risks. Through the GEE environment, we achieved near real-time preprocessing of several geospatial datasets to create detailed variables required in estimating deforestation risks and energy demand. Findings reveal the complex interplay between urbanization, infrastructure, energy demand, and deforestation in Uganda. While urbanization reduces direct rural deforestation pressure, it intensifies energy demand, exacerbating deforestation indirectly. This study advances GIScience and supports sustainable energy policies aligned with SDGs 7, 13, and 15, offering evidence-based insights for mitigating deforestation while ensuring energy security and climate resilience.

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6. Biographies

Dan Abudu is a PhD student at the Energy and Bioproducts Research Institute, Aston University. His research interests include geospatial modelling of land use land cover, sustainable biomass for climate and energy security, and urbanisation.

Lucy Bastin is a Professor in the School of Computer Science and Digital Technologies at Aston University. She combines industrial software development experience with her established multi-disciplinary research links formed over >25 years in academia. She spent several years at the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission as Lead Developer on the Digital Observatory for Protected areas (<https://dopa-explorer.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) and East Africa lead for the BIOPAMA project (<https://biopama.org/>).

Katie Chong is a Senior Systems Engineer at the Energy Systems Catapult. She has keen interests and expertise in sustainability and energy systems modelling. Katie previously worked as a senior lecturer in chemical engineering at Aston University and has extensive industrial experience in the paper industry, as well as experience as a bioenergy consultant.

Mirjam Roeder is a Professor at the Energy and Bioproducts Research Institute (EBRI) at Aston University. She leads EBRI Systems Analysis group and has a robust background in sustainable bioenergy systems and the transition to low-carbon societies. Her research interests focus on bioenergy sustainability including environmental, social and economic aspects.

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